

**THE ROLE OF ROAD TRANSPORT IN THE OPERATION OF LOGISTICS CENTERS.
DEVELOPMENT OF ROAD TRANSPORT IN AZERBAIJAN**

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**РОЛЬ АВТОМОБИЛЬНОГО ТРАНСПОРТА В РАБОТЕ ЛОГИСТИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕНТРОВ.
РАЗВИТИЕ АВТОМОБИЛЬНОГО ТРАНСПОРТА В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ**

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Abstract

One of the most important areas of logistics is transportation management. Transportation can have a direct impact on the country's economy, both domestic and foreign. Each type of transport has its own characteristics - positive and negative aspects. The study is devoted to the positive effects of road transport on the country's economy and enterprise income, and to the analysis of the development dynamics of road transport in Azerbaijan. Car transport is considered a fast and flexible mode of transport as it carries out transportation to every area of the country, even rural areas. Logical generalization, comparison and statistical analysis methods were used in the research.

Аннотация

Одним из важнейших направлений логистики является управление транспортом. Транспорт может оказывать непосредственное влияние на экономику страны, как внутреннюю, так и внешнюю. Каждый вид транспорта имеет свои особенности - положительные и отрицательные стороны. Исследование посвящено положительному влиянию автомобильного транспорта на экономику страны и доходы предприятий, а также анализу динамики развития автомобильного транспорта в Азербайджане. Автомобильный транспорт считается быстрым и гибким видом транспорта, поскольку осуществляет перевозки в любой регион страны, даже в сельскую местность. В исследовании использовались методы логического обобщения, сравнения и статистического анализа.

Keywords: road transport, logistics, logistics center, cargo transportation

Ключевые слова: автомобильный транспорт, логистика, логистический центр, грузоперевозки

The term logistics means skillful calculation in Greek. Although it was formed in the military field in the early days, it was later used in the product circulation. Of course, the development of logistics in the economic field was related to the need to reduce transportation, inventory, and time costs. Transport - transportation aims to effectively and efficiently implement the process of delivering products from the first producer to the final consumer. Transportation costs account for one third of total logistics costs. For this reason, reducing these costs is considered one of the important factors. In general, the role of transport in logistics processes is more complex than we think. Delays in delivery, changes in product quality during transportation, delivery to wrong addresses, failure to expect efficiency during transportation cause the enterprise to be in a difficult situation in front of the customer and financial loss. Therefore, transport has an important place in ensuring efficiency and effectiveness in logistics processes and in the economy in general. [5], [6]

Since transportation is one of the costliest stages among logistics processes, improving transportation efficiency can increase overall performance. So, we can come to the conclusion that the ability of the enterprise to increase its competitiveness and customer satisfac-

tion directly depends on increasing the quality of logistics activities, mainly transport. The efficiency of transport requires the correct use of transport modes. Each mode of transport has its own advantages. Some have advantages for fast delivery, some for safety, some for low cost, some for long distance shipping. In this regard, the presence of intermodal transportation brings more advantages. Since this study is devoted to the role of road transport, let's give the main priority to this type of transport. [2], [7]

The advantages of car transport can be listed as follows:

- ✓ Compared to other types of transport, it is relatively cheap and fast. So, it can be cheaper than air and sea transport. The reason for this is that both vehicles need additional vehicles for transporting products;

- ✓ It is effective in short transports;

- ✓ Door-to-door delivery is possible - in areas where the structure of the infrastructure allows, the presence of highways in many countries of the world and the possibility of transportation make it possible for automobile transport to carry out transportation without interruption;

- ✓ No intermediaries;

- ✓ It is possible to combine several products and deliver the same vehicle to several addresses;

✓It is flexible according to other types of transport;

✓The presence of GPS systems ensures safety;

✓It is possible to overflow all types of products.

[10]

The joint use of automobile transport with other types of transport makes it possible to carry out transportation to areas where there are no highways. If proper planning is done, it is possible to carry out cheaper and faster product transportation over long distances thanks to intermodal transportation. [8]

During transportation by road, the conditions for loading products must be strictly observed. The first thing to consider is that the products should be delivered first to the customer's location and the last to be loaded onto the vehicle. Of course, when loading the products, the composition of the product, the characteristics of the vehicle - height, width, etc.), the physical characteristics of the product, etc. factors must be considered. [3]

Freight transportation is one of the main aspects of the economy in Azerbaijan. Of course, there is legislation to regulate this process. "Rules for the transportation of goods by road transport" include the organization of local and international transportation, requirements for the transportation of individual cargoes,

regulation of relations between the parties, their rights and duties, and drafting of acts. Also, it is important to take into account the relevant customs regulations when transporting goods by road. [4]

One of the advantages of road transport is the possibility of using different means of transport according to the type and weight of transported goods. [9]

In addition to all this, of course, there are also negative aspects of car transport. The most important of them are environmental problems. Of course, we cannot deny the share of the increase in the number of vehicles in atmospheric pollution. Air pollution from different types of transport poses a serious threat to people's health. Currently, there are 1645253 number of trucks in Azerbaijan. About 30-40% of these cars have been inspected and found to be serviceable. Various ways are being sought to solve this problem, which is recognized all over the world. Thus, the introduction of autonomous and electric cars to the market is designed to prevent air pollution. [11]

The role of logistics in the economy of Azerbaijan is also great. Transportation in Azerbaijan is carried out by all types of transport separately and combined (intermodal) means of transport. If we analyze for 2012-2022:

Table 1.
Changes in road transport for 2012-2022 compared to previous years, in percentage

	In 2013 compared to 2012	In 2014 Compared to 2013	In 2015 Compared to 2014	In 2016 Compared to 2015	In 2017 Compared to 2016	In 2018 Compared to 2017	In 2019 compared to 2018	In 2020 compared to 2019	In 2021 compared to 2020	In 2022 compared to 2021
The cargo was carried, thousand tons	+6.01	+2.7	+7	+2.8	+2.4	+3.1	+4	-28.2	+0.9	+12
by natural persons	+7.5	+2.6	+6.9	+2.7	+2.3	+3	+3.9	-28.5	-7.2	+9.8
Cargo circulation, million ton-km	+6.11	+2.8	+7	+2.8	+2.3	+3.2	+4	-49.8	+7.09	+23.11
by natural persons	+6.19	+2.71	+6.9	+2.7	+2.2	+3.1	+3.9	-50.2	+4.92	+17.6
Income from transportation, thousand manats	+10.14	+11.35	+10.65	+7.64	+4.85	+9.66	+32.02	-35.91	+7.84	+32.8
from cargo transportation	+10.9	+11.5	+10.9	+6.52	+3	+2.4	+56.51	-35.66	+0.43	+22.54
Transportation costs, thousand manats	+17.34	+18.44	+16.82	+14.9	+13.72	+12.56	-5.52	-36.8	+12.56	+34.24
to cargo transportation	+17.4	+18.5	+17.5	+16.1	+15.5	+14.7	-14.78	-36.7	+9.84	+24.15
Average annual number of employees, people	+3.81	-17.76	+44.25	-1.04	+3.33	+1.54	+17.98	-16.33	-4.28	+5.94
Average monthly nominal salary, AZN	+6.31	-10.3	+14.95	+11.62	+9.77	+4.68	+5	-2.32	+1.15	+8.81

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

As can be seen from Table 1, there is an increase in the main indicators in the road transport segment of logistic transport. In general, the indicators of cargo transportation decreased by 9.5% compared to the base period, including the decrease of 11% for individuals. The observed decrease in the analyzed periods was 7% in freight turnover, including 6.8% for individuals. Revenues from cargo transportation increased by 15.3%. Although there was a noticeable increase in profit, expenses also increased by 62%.

Table 2.

Number of vehicles, at the end of the year, units

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	1,135,936	1,232,678	1,291,008	1,322,610	1,330,551	1,342,324	1,370,574	1,418,404	1,473,563	1,566,743	1,645,253
cargo vehicles	130,019	133,637	141,126	141,273	141,525	142,857	147,343	150,547	154,659	161,279	168,705
special purpose vehicles	11,936	13,427	11,282	11,063	11,158	11,024	11,232	11,924	11,613	12,233	13,097
others	5,740	6,474	7,533	9,621	9,927	10,218	10,623	11,057	11,992	13,109	12,369
Trailers and semi-trailers	11,424	12,350	13,104	13,744	13,971	14,518	15,412	16,840	18,110	19,762	23,010
Cars falling on highways every 1 km	60	65	68	70	70	71	71	74	77	81	87
Passenger cars per 1000 people	104	113	117	119	118	118	119	123	127	135	141

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

Analyzing Table 2, we see that during the years 2012-2022, a 69% increase is observed in the number of vehicles used in freight transportation. The observed 62% increase in transportation costs can be explained by the increase in the number of vehicles.

Table 3.

The main indicators of transport in the CIS countries - Freight transportation in the transport sector, million tons												
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
Azerbaijan	210.9	217.9	222	222.4	222.5	226.4	230.1	235.3	188.6	193.9	218.7	
Belarus	484.4	471.2	467.5	447.2	417.6	439.5	455.5	427.8	398.7	384.9	0	
Armenia	11.2	12.3	9.2	9.3	18.6	25.5	26.3	11.2	11.5	13.8	15.3	
Kazakhstan	3231.8	3508	3749.8	3733.8	631.5	737.4	813.7	838.6	829	874.1	890.8	
Kyrgyzstan	26.9	27.9	28.9	29.7	31.2	31.9	33	34.2	24.7	28.6	44.3	
Moldova	27.9	30.8	32.9	30.6	32.2	37.8	38.2	33.1	20.4	23.6	24.2	
Uzbekistan	1329.3	1387.1	1458.9	1527	1132.5	1146.2	1243	1319.8	1366.7	1420.2	1420.9	
Russia	4382.6	4320	4203.8	4083.5	4133.9	4282.4	4351.1	4211.6	3998.6	4161.1	3971.8	
Tajikistan	52	52.2	54.4	53.9	55.5	54.9	54.4	51.2	57.1	66.3	84.4	
Turkmenistan	0	0	0	0	0	0	515.1	524.7	528.4	551.4	566.4	
Ukraine	771.9	759.4	672.1	601.8	624.6	636.8	624.6	676.1	599.9	621.3	0	

**) Except for cargo transported for commercial purposes by individual entrepreneurs*

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

As can be seen from Table 3, there are numerous reductions or stops in the transportation of feathers across the CIS countries for various reasons. Stable growth is observed in Azerbaijan, excluding the pandemic period (2020). Thus, there is a total increase of 4% for the analyzed periods.

Table 4.

The main indicators of transport in the CIS countries - Freight turnover in the transport sector, billion ton-km												
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
Azerbaijan	90.1	90.9	93.5	92.8	90.8	92	93.3	89.7	76.3	78.7	90.3	
Belarus	131.7	130.8	131.4	126	125.8	133.3	138.8	130.8	123.2	118.8	88.6	
Armenia	4.3	4.2	4.2	3.7	3.9	4.3	4.4	4.8	4.7	5.1	5.3	
Kazakhstan	478	495.4	554.9	546.3	365.1	406.7	447.2	438.4	436.2	471.4	467.8	
Kyrgyzstan	2.3	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.4	2.6	2.8	2.9	2.4	2.6	2.8	
Moldova	5.1	5.6	5.5	5.1	5.3	6.1	6.2	5.8	5	5.6	6.4	
Uzbekistan	83.4	83.7	85.7	86.9	65.3	66.9	71.3	72.6	66.9	74.8	75.5	
Russia	4935	4958.4	4955.1	4981.6	5075.6	5367.2	5515.1	5554.7	5279.2	5576.4	5433.1	
Tajikistan	6	6.2	5.5	5.7	5.3	5.6	6	7	7.2	7.9	9.6	
Turkmenistan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Ukraine	394.3	381.4	335.4	316	324.2	343.3	331.9	338.9	290.4	289.6	0	

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

It can be seen from Table 4 that in the analyzed period, freight turnover for CIS countries decreased during the pandemic period in Azerbaijan (2019-2020), but between 2012 and 2022, no decrease was observed, it was almost stable is left.

Table 5.

The structure of cargo transportation by types of transport, in % relative to the total

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Railway	11.0	10.6	9.8	7.7	6.9	6.4	6.0	6.5	7.8	7.8	8.6
Sea	5.9	5.3	4.5	3.0	2.6	3.7	3.6	2.5	3.2	2.8	3.4
Air	0.04	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2
Pipeline	27.1	26.6	27.7	27.4	26.8	25.8	25.4	24.9	29.7	31.1	30.2
oil pipeline	20.5	20.0	20.6	20.5	19.8	18.8	18.0	16.5	18.4	18.1	17.3
gas pipeline	6.6	6.6	7.1	6.9	7.0	7.0	7.4	8.4	11.3	13.0	12.9
Road	56.0	57.4	57.9	61.8	63.6	64.0	64.9	66.0	59.1	58.0	57.6

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

Analyzing Table 5, we see that there is a decrease in railway, sea, and air transport types during the observed periods. However, we can observe an increase in the vehicle type of transport. This is due to the advantages of automobile transport, which we highlighted at the beginning of the study. By giving the indicators given in Table 5 in the form of a diagram, we can see more clearly the changes (increase and decrease), as well as the difference in transportation between the car mode of transport and other modes of transport:

Graph 1.

Source: The graph was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data

Table 6.

		The structure of freight turnover by types of transport, in % relative to the total											
		2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Railway	8.6	9.1	8.8	7.9	6.7	5.7	5.0	4.8	5.7	6.4	6.7	7.9	
Sea	5.7	5.6	5.1	4.4	3.2	3.3	4.8	4.9	3.7	4.3	3.9	3.8	
Air	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.8	1.0	1.1	3.0	3.6	3.1	
Pipeline	72.0	70.1	70.1	71.7	72.8	72.6	71.6	71.2	69.9	74.8	73.8	72.4	
oil pipeline	67.7	65.7	65.2	66.3	67.4	67.1	65.9	65.0	62.2	64.6	60.5	59.1	
gas pipeline	4.3	4.4	4.9	5.4	5.4	5.5	5.7	6.2	7.7	10.2	13.3	13.3	
Road	13.5	14.8	15.5	15.5	16.7	17.6	17.8	18.1	19.6	11.5	12.0	12.8	

Source: The table was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data, [1]

Analyzing the indicators given in Table 6, one can observe the growth until the pandemic period, i.e. until 2019. While 2020 is a 0.9% decrease compared to the previous year, 2021 shows a 0.5% increase compared to 2020, and 2022 shows a 0.8% increase compared to 2021. The noted changes are consistent with the increases and decreases we have seen in previous analyses. Let's express the changes in transport types for 2012-2022 with a diagram below:

Graph 1.

Source: The graph was compiled by the author based on official stat.gov.az data

Result

The creation of logistics centers in Azerbaijan will be observed with an increase in logistics flows. It is for this reason that certain steps are taken at the state level to eliminate the problems that have arisen or may arise on the types of transport. Since we have analyzed the indicators of road transport in the study, we can say that in addition to digitized processes, the application of green technologies is also an important factor in reducing the damage caused by road transport to the environment. With this method, we can both protect the environment and increase investment attraction. The use of new technologies, mainly green technologies, can lead to more flexible, faster, cheaper and less time-consuming process management. It should be noted that Azerbaijan not only fully modernizes the entire transport infrastructure, but also continues to develop transport communications in the territories freed from Armenian occupation. This will lead to a further increase in the already growing transportation indicators and a positive trend of income growth.

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